

A Study of various techniques on video error concealment – Review

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Abstract

The topic of error management and concealment in video communication is becoming more relevant since there is a rising interest in video distribution across problematic channels such as wireless networks and the internet. This study examines the approaches used for mistake control and concealment. These techniques are classified into three groups based on the roles that the decoder and encoder play in the underlying methodologies. Forward error hiding comprises ways for adding redundancy at the original end to improve the error resistance of coded bit streams. Error hiding via postprocessing refers to decoder operations that restore damaged sections depending on image and video signal properties. Finally, interactive error hiding includes strategies that rely on a communication between the origin and destination. The article discusses both current research activity and worldwide standards practice. The topic of error management and concealment in video communication is becoming more relevant since there is a rising interest in video distribution across problematic channels such as wireless networks and the Internet. This study examines the strategies that are being developed for mistake control and concealment in recent years. These techniques are classified into three groups based on the roles that the decoder and encoder play in the underpinning methodologies. Forward error hiding comprises ways for adding redundancies at the initial end to improve the error resistance of coded bit streams. Error hiding via post-processing refers to decoder operations that restore damaged sections depending on video and image signal properties.

Keywords: Error concealment, error control in video transport, video communications.

Introduction

Error concealment is a video delivery system's last line of protection against transmission mistakes. In terms of video coding norms, it is a non-normative additional processing action that occurs after the current frame has been decoded and before it is displayed, or, in the event of complete frame loss, after the missing frame has been discovered and before the next frame is decoded. Because of the compression methods used, encoded video bitstreams are particularly vulnerable to channel faults. Because of the widespread use of prediction methods (e.g., for motion compensation, differential DC transform coefficient coding, and motion vector coding) and variable length coding (e.g., in entropy coding for motion vectors and residual data), a single uncorrected channel error can corrupt adjacent spatiotemporal regions of a video signal.

Forward error correction coding is commonly used in the video transmission chain to secure video packets before they are sent across a channel to the receiver. When the quantity of mistakes exceeds the error correction code's rectification capability, many communication systems will initiate an auto-repeat request (ARQ) operation to retransmit missing packets. ARQ approaches, however, are inapplicable in multicast transmission, as clients

encounter varying channel conditions. Even with single-cast dissemination, the number of ARQs is sometimes restricted due to real-time rendering or buffering limitations. When these restrictions are exceeded, packets are not successfully received and are typically not transmitted to the application layer, resulting in missing block of pixels in the decode frame or entire frame losses.

The level of loss will be determined by the packetization used at the broadcaster and the severity of channel faults [1]. Missing packet can also occur when delays surpass the restrictions set by the delay-sensitive characteristics of video applications, which need video packets to be presented at specific time intervals or lost otherwise. To avoid a significant reduction in received video quality owing to within and inter-frame propagation of such faults, error resilience features at the encoder and error concealment at the decoder are required [2-5].

Fault resilience is the practice of introducing redundancy to a stream of videos during encoding in order to avoid severe visual quality loss at the decoder in the case of mistakes. A classic example is the utilization of numerous slices inside a single frame. Slices are individually decodable units made up of multiple coding elements or macroblocks¹ (for example, a row). They offer redundancy to the encoded stream through headers, as well as by defining permissible limitations for intra-frame pixel value and side information prediction.

Their use stops intra-frame error propagation. Without them, a lost packet would result in a complete frame loss, making error hiding at the decoder extremely difficult (if not impossible). Other error resilience tools include redundant slices (data repeated with lower fidelity), data division followed by unequal error protection (separation of motion vectors, intra data, and residual), flexible macro block ordering and instantaneous decoder refresh frames (IDR frames) [6]. In contrast to error resilience, which serves to preserve the bitstream from loss, error concealment (EC) is a receiver-based method that estimates and replaces material lost during transmission before rendering. To achieve this recovery, concealment strategies must take use of the correlations between an injured macroblock (MB) and its adjacent neighbours in the same or prior frame(s). There are two basic forms of concealing: temporal error concealment (TEC) and spatially error concealment (SEC).

In the spatial domain, the lost area of the frame is concealed using the spatially neighbouring pixels. These methods exploit the correlations among the neighboring pixels within a frame. In the temporal domain, the available contents from the previous and/or future frames are used for loss concealment. If the lost area is relatively large (as is the case in HEVC and VVC), spatial domain is not effective, since pixels are very far apart from each other to be useful. For this reason, in this paper we consider only temporal domain techniques.

Figure 1 Boundary Matching Error

Figure 2 External boundary matching Error

Temporal error concealment methods calculate missing motion vectors (MVs), which are then used for motion compensated temporal substitute of lost MBs, whereas spatial error concealment methods predict missing data using spatially adjacent macroblocks and typically use some form of interpolation. Despite the great number of techniques documented in the literature, the majority of them include identical processes with little differences. The reader will be guided through these procedures for the three fundamental concealing stages: spatial error concealment, temporal error concealment and mode selection.

Table 1.0 Methods for Spatial Error Concealment

Boundary pixel selection	After identifying the missing macroblocks, we must determine which border pixels from nearby MBs will participate in the hiding procedure. Boundary pixels from previously suppressed MBs are often regarded untrustworthy and omitted from the subsequent processes. However, in some cases where there are insufficient trusted neighbors, their usage may be required.
Interpolation of lost pixels	To replace the missing pixels, an interpolation method must be used, with the specified border pixels as input. Salama et al. [13] used bilinear interpolation (BI) to replace missing pixels with a weighted average of the border pixels. This technique will provide smooth approximations of the missing pixels/MBs. This method will produce satisfactory results in smooth or highly textured surfaces.
Directional interpolation	To circumvent the issues raised above, the direction of edges going through the absence of macroblock(s) can be approximated, followed by directional interpolation (DI) along the estimated edge direction(s).

The missing pixels are restored with some temporally or geographically neighboring pixels using error concealment techniques, either with or without further processing. The video content and the loss location determine the quality of error hiding. Error hiding is more difficult for complicated and moving items in front of complex backdrops than it is for the video's static sections. For certain applications, the error concealment distortion for the lossy frame itself may be negligible and unimportant. But because video codecs are predictive, concealing distortion may readily spread to subsequent frames, often rendering the movie completely useless. It should be noted that the present frame cannot be completely error-free rebuilt and will contain erroneous areas even if all of its packets are accurately available and one or both of their predictor references have loss hidden sections. By serving as a reference for subsequent frames, this frame containing incorrect sections may further propagate the problem into those frames. If one lossy frame is mistakenly concealed by using the erroneous frame, the issue gets worse.

Literature Survey (Recent Work on Error Concealment)

The Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) of the ISO/IEC Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) and the ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG) together developed the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC)[1] standard. The primary objective of HEVC is to achieve a bit rate reduction of around 50% while improving compression performance in comparison to current standards. Almost all of the current H.264/AVC applications are addressed by HEVC, which focuses on two main issues: higher video resolution and greater utilization of parallel processing systems.

Once more, JCT-VC is working on a project called Versatile Video Coding (VVC) [2], which has two main objectives. First, it will offer compression efficiency that surpasses that of HEVC. Secondly, it will be extremely adaptable, making it useful in a wider variety of uses than those covered by the previous standards. Ultra-high definition video (e.g., 3840 x 2160 or 7620 x 4320 pixels), bit depth of 10 bits, high dynamic range, broad color gamut movies, and immersive media applications are among the applications that stand out in particular.

Consequently, these codecs' main objectives are to accommodate earlier applications while also improving coding efficiency for videos with increasing resolutions. It's noteworthy to note, nevertheless, that HEVC and VVC require better error/loss concealment than H.264/AVC since they lack error resilience features like Redundant Slice and Flexible MacroBlock Ordering (FMO).

In "A study on the HEVC performance over lossy networks," author[3] compared the experimental results of HEVC's worse error resilience performance to that of H.264/AVC. The issue is because hardly little thought was put to VVC and HEVC's resilience to channel defects during their primary design, which was high quality and high resolution video streaming.

Internet of Things (IoT) is a new application domain of error concealment described in [4], where objects are networked together over the internet to exchange data for a shared goal. The information that was sent was in the form of data, but the need for Multimedia Internet of Things (M-IoT), sometimes called Internet of Multimedia Things (IoMT), has increased because to the quick development of IoT systems and applications. Numerous applications in this setting need real-time video streaming, as detailed in [11]. A few instances include the remote observation of a plant, vehicles on the road, or people inside a designated area. High resolution video feeds in real time are necessary for applications like health care monitoring and urban surveillance.

Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) [5] has been suggested as a web transport protocol for the Internet of Things. With less used bandwidth and energy, CoAP is intended to provide an IoT function like to that of HTTP on the conventional Internet. Although there are further IoT application layers, it should be emphasized that CoAP is more pertinent, particularly for media and video transmission.

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First, it will offer compression efficiency that surpasses that of HEVC. Secondly, it will be extremely adaptable, making it useful in a wider variety of applications than those covered by the previous standards. Ultra-high definition video (e.g., 3840 x 2160 or 7620 x 4320 pixels), bit depth of 10 bits, high dynamic range, broad color gamut movies, and immersive media applications are among the applications that stand out in particular.

Experimental research on HEVC's worse error resilience performance in comparison to H.264/AVC can be found in [7]. The issue is because hardly little thought was put to VVC and HEVC's resilience to channel defects during their primary design, which was high quality and high resolution video streaming. However, compared to H.264/AVC, their compression ratios are significantly greater, making them more susceptible to channel faults. According to our studies, HEVC is 20%–30% more effective at compression for low resolution videos like QSIF and about 50% more efficient at compression for HD and higher quality films than H.264/AVC.

Moreover, tests in [7] demonstrate that for similar perceptual quality, VVC has a about 35% higher compression efficiency than HEVC. As a result, it is quite likely that in many networks, HEVC will mostly replace H.264/AC in the near future, and that VVC will eventually replace HEVC. For these video codecs, error hiding techniques are becoming increasingly more crucial, since they both lack the error resilience capabilities of H.264/AVC.

MVs of the previously accessible frames can be utilized in a recursive manner [8] to improve the recovered MV as shown in [8]. This study takes the approach of refining $\hat{m}_i$ by using the difference of MVs in subsequent frames. The MV disparities between the actual values and their are computed for the correctly received MBs in the previous frame in a refined region; the value of with the highest occurrences is then utilized for fine tuning.

Every 4×4 block has a refining area that is defined by the greatest difference of the MVs in the two previously received frames that were received successfully. This method is predicated on the correlation between the MVs' differences in subsequent frames as well as their correlation. However, unless an item moves with a constant acceleration, the former correlation may not always be valid and logical.

[9] uses for loss concealment, however its MV is unstable if the co-located block has a significant residual or is an intra-coded block. If possible, these blocks are combined (a partition merging example). Subsequently, the average of the MVs of the neighboring blocks is assigned to the amalgamated block. While it is beneficial to process unreliable MVs further and do more research to improve MV recovery, not all losses and moving objects will be suitable candidates for merging MVs and assigning a global MV. It is evident that this method works well in a small number of unique situations.

[10] uses a variety of block sizes for loss concealment, including 32x32, 16x16, 8x8, 4x4, 2x2, and 1x1 pixels. The median of the MVs of the top, top-left, top-right, left, and co-located blocks is then used to compute MV. The final loss concealed frame is calculated by weight-averaging the frames that result from each size, which may lead to a different loss concealed frame. According to the motion trajectory provided by the MVs used for block replacement, the weights are inversely proportional to the Sum of Absolute Difference (SAD) of the respective pixels.

There are two problems with this approach: first, it is unreasonable to apply the same size to the whole lossy region; second, for HEVC and VVC losses, the neighboring MVs are unavailable for the innermost blocks of the lossy area.

Each pixel's MV in [11] is determined by averaging the weights of the nearest accessible pixels' MVs surrounding the missing MB. The distance between the lost pixel and the nearby accessible pixels determines the weights in an inverse manner. In this manner, each pixel's MV is retrieved and utilized to replace the pixels from the previous frame. Even if it can be complicated, it's not always accurate to correlate a pixel's motion with that of its neighboring pixels in adjacent blocks. A little moving item, for instance, has no connection to the backdrop that is motionless.

A similar concept was put out in [12], however non-covered blocks or blocks that almost equally overlap with several MVs are subject to a different regulation. In case of a failed projection, meaning that the overlapping area is not zero but not large enough, MVE is not utilized and instead is employed. In the event that there are some block overlaps but no dominating MV or no coverage at all, a median MV is substituted in a window of 12 by 12 pixels. Certain criteria are required, and in the study they are empirically determined and verified for movies of H.264/AVC and QCIF sizes. An appropriate solution for

the non-projected blocks is introduced by this approach. Nevertheless, the co-located blocks of these blocks frequently have intramode coding; as a result, there is no median MV or MV for obtaining $\hat{m}_i$. In other words, non-projected blocks continue to be a problem for MVE techniques. Non-efficient utilization of the spatially accurately accessible pixels is another problem with MVE techniques.

Motion compensated pixel replacement uses the mean of a collection of extrapolated mean vectors (MVs) for each pixel, which is derived from the work provided in [13]. This collection consists of the MV derived using MVE, the MV derived from extrapolation using weighted averaging, and lastly the MV of pixels derived using the technique described in [13]. The average of MVE is applied if a pixel is not covered by any overlapping region but the contained block possesses MVE. Once more, it is a suitable option for hiding a complete frame loss. As previously indicated, this method works with both HEVC and VVC but does not take use of the available pixels surrounding the lossy region.

Conclusion

With the increased interest in video distribution across unreliable channels like wireless networks and the Internet, the topic of error management and concealing in video communication is becoming more and more essential. The methods for error control and concealment that have been developed during the last ten to fifteen years are reviewed in this study. Based on the roles that both encoder and decoder play in the underlying methodologies, these techniques are categorized into three groups. In order to improve the error robustness of the coded bit streams, forward error hiding techniques involve adding redundancy at the source end. Postprocessing methods at the decoder to restore areas of damage based on features of video and image signals are referred to as error concealment. Finally, methods that rely on a conversation between the point of origin and destination are covered by interactive error hiding. The practice of international standards as well as ongoing research projects are discussed.

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